

Importance of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in Medical and Physical Health Education

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Abstract

The growth in aids in usage of technologies and communication tools are prime challenges affecting Physical Health care workers today. This dilemma is not only specific to current analytic approaches offered by major establishments, which are extensively utilised in research-related areas; it is also of significant concern in Physical Health education. Usage of simulators, internet and interactive educational has proven to be an effective teaching-learning tool mostly at the university level. Many colleges are encouraging the incorporation of skills into their curricula and finding it easier to resolve the difficulty faced by this technological boom. Medical institutions will have to be well updated for this in advance.

Keywords: Physical Health, ICT, Medical education;

Introduction

For a period, there has been extensive international discussion of the potential of ICTs in order to address demands and foster development and have a greater impact on the Physical Health and social welfare of deprived and marginalised populations.

As per the World Health Organization, their use in this sector is regarded to achieve a range of framework objectives; 1 hence in this field of Physical Health they are described as instruments for fostering contacts and the dissemination of information through electronic means, in order to enhance individuals' well-being. This definition

refers to the vast spectrum of innovations, from radio and television to telecommunications, computers and Internet technologies.

The recruitment of skilled human capital in their jobs is another problem facing this field. This is taking place in an environment characterized by the incorporation and assimilation of rapidly developing information, a growing number of students and a steady shift from a "traditional" type of teaching organisation to a more "productive and engaging" model, where the student is the key player in the teaching-learning phase.

The teaching of the Internet has proved beneficial in medical education and various

educational institutions have taken advantage of the distance learning process, such as educational materials, simulators, communications (web conferences), e-portfolios, research and validated medicine.

As a part of this technological boom, disciplines that improve expertise through their usage have now been included in the curricula of various medical education institutions around the world, 3 the following work is set as an aim to explain the effect that the ICT world has on Physical Health and medical education.

Information and Communication Technologies in Physical Health field

The power provided by technical advancement in this field worldwide provides promising experiences; however, study needs to be done to remove the challenges that exist in order to fulfil its full potential. The most ambitious forecasts show that the computer controlled and interconnected future not only means progress in the amount of workers and efficiency and furthermore guarantees increased access to services that increase quality of life.

They are valuable resources as an instrument for pursuing continued education and lifelong learning; they can allow practitioners in the field to provide access to up-to-date information and to be educated in the development of medical knowledge; they are a framework for delivering a broad variety of resources, ranging from enhancing communication of human Physical Health to medical emergencies. Particularly in hard-to-reach areas or in disadvantaged neighbourhoods.

One of the most commonly adopted technology in modern years since its introduction has always been the Internet. Although its origins dates back at least to 1969, its true potential was achieved in 1990 whenever the HTML language was developed by a community of physicists headed by the English person Tim Berners-Lee. This network is constantly a repository of information and expertise,

even in medicine, information is readily accessible and it is already commonplace for patients and their relatives to use that to seek information regarding these programs and their applications. Increased usage of web resources and technology is promising alternative ways of engagement, collaboration and involvement throughout the Physical Health care industry.

Additional information is being generated at an overwhelming pace every day and the list of journals, databases, and other outlets that life sciences and research scientists need to work with will become more of a challenge than an opportunity today. As a result, proper knowledge processing becomes a crucial element of scientists' existence, specifically if they interact with inclusion, like biological systems. There are various attempts at restructuring the sources of the biological knowledge required to make it more usable.

Physical Health treatment includes constructive, informative practices. From an economic point of view, the Physical Health sector carries out two major actions: care or disease prevention, and diagnostic practices for their diagnosis and collection, utilization, connectivity and storing of knowledge. It is therefore safe to claim that computer advances leading to the provision and distribution of information and to introducing digital innovations, such as computers and the Internet, have a huge effect on Physical Health-care services.

Conceptually, the promise of these innovations in the Physical Health sector lives in their position as mediators between differentially endowed divisions of the Physical Health care system, the service provider and the recipients. As long as this role is concerned, they pledge to be a stronger way of delivering basic Physical Health care, and a mechanism that aims to reshape the structure and to make it more effective. Given their mediating position, their effect depends not only on the lack of foresight or vulnerabilities of the managers to implement them as instruments, but also on entry,

distribution and capacity for networking between various segments of the Physical Health system.

In fact, the opportunities provided by ICT in the abstract might not apply. An illustration of this is seen in telemedicine, which aims to provide patients with the latest medical care and care, irrespective of where they are based. The largest limitation in this region is proximity to higher capacity and the expense of transferring data with therapeutic guidance and complicated medical pictures. These constraints are more extreme in developed countries, where even connectivity through telephone lines is restricted and broadband infrastructure is not yet accessible in all geographic regions and shared facilities, or it is very costly to supply the whole population in need such that it has a real effect.

Technological transition presents both threats and opportunities. The basic task is to train doctors about the use of technology and to rehabilitate medical practice. The prospects lie in the ability of information technology to improve medical practice by rendering it more successful.

The right use of these steps favours the supply of better knowledge to practitioners in the field and acts as a way of strengthening the conditions of the Physical Health care system. It is thus more convenient, with underdeveloped nations, to focus on training Physical Health practitioners in the potential usage of ICT, supplying them with access and accessibility, which would extend the benefits to a larger number of people.

Information and Communication Technologies in medical education

It is important, first, to consider the world in which they would work, to train subsequent generations of physicians. Integrative teaching requires the development of a potential Physical Health environment in which medical students, teachers, and consumers of Physical Health care function together. This training takes place in an atmosphere where technical advances and knowledge bursts predominate.

In higher education study, data shows that ICT has a beneficial effect on the promotion of learning quality. The role they hold in the medical education is also being in modern days, and the need to have a group of teachers skilled in the usage of computer technology must be taken into consideration. This involves the usage of reference databases, electronic medical reports, and online links to clinical and instructional content.

At present, advances are being produced in the research programs of several medical universities aimed at maximizing their potentialities, for which there are constant arrangements both for the teaching of the topic and for the content of Medical Informatics. Expanding expertise in the Physical Health sciences includes teaching in new abilities to empower consumers and promote access to immediate details. Theoretical and realistic instruction of undergraduate and doctoral medical and Physical Health sciences involves basic student interaction with advanced procedures and unique medical instruments complemented by computers. The teaching of knowledge science and its substance are of considerable significance as part of curricular studies in medical schools.

According to Schneider and Eisenberg, the effective medical education program must react to ICT problems and must therefore:

The possession of simple programming skills should be a prerequisite of newly enrolled medical students. Early introduction of applied medical informatics to raise understanding with basic informational instruments in practice (includes the use of computerized medical data, use of educational resources in digital format, and intensive use of the Internet). Medical informatics training should be a priority for medical educators, to create, maintaining and updating the infrastructure that will maintain this technology. The Academic Centres of Medicine must test the software used to ensure its correct functioning and the correct transmission of knowledge.

Research and training on the confidentiality and security of electronic records and communications should be incorporated into medical education.

A task force of Physical Health informatics educators and doctors addressed the developing role of education technology in February 2010 at the International Conference on Faculty Growth and suggested the usage of them in different universities as part of the medical education. It has been concluded that technology fully changes this method and that many converging patterns are found, which illustrate why medical educators need to be trained in the present decade. These developments include the proliferation in additional information, expertise and digital medical documents, the rise and speed of transformation towards a new age, the emergence of new education technology.

The recommendations for addressing the challenges of new education technologies with a view to medical education during this decade have been: the use of technology to provide and support student experience, which is not possible as a substitute but more than a supplement between head-to-head practises; further attention is given to simple teaching-learning concepts.

There are multiple applications in the world to develop responsible and quality teaching using the benefits of these technologies. The creation of multimedia, web-based courses, databases and reference materials has been developed to maintain continuing education in Physical Health personnel.

Because of the high level of informational content, new knowledge and techniques are essential critical thinking skills to distinguish between true and scientific information from that which is not. Current curricula already include these skills for medical students in their courses. Cuba does not escape this reality, and Physical Health-related careers include subjects that help students gain computer and information skills. For example, the subject of Medical Informatics is taught in the first semester of

the first year, with 60 hours/classes, and in the next semester of the second year the subject of Research method and Biostatistics with equal hours/classes.

Using information technology addresses the needs of knowledge by the student, all under the guidance and advice of the teacher, who not only fulfils the educational function but is extremely important in the fulfilment of the regulatory and emotional functions of educational communication. The evaluative component is provided only by the human being and not by new technologies, and therefore the teacher should therefore be someone who provides the student a perspective modulated by their training and values and which enables the integration and development of the educational component into teaching.

Conclusions

ICTs are growing at a dizzying pace every day with a significant impact on the Physical Health and medical education sectors. It is necessary to prepare professionals so they can take up this challenge, a task that must be carried out as soon as they enter the medical university, so that the activities and teachings relating to its use of ICT already are included with the curricula of medical universities.

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